

A Holistic Approach to Patient Privacy: A Current Review Covering Ethical, Technological, and Educational Dimensions

Hasta Mahremiyetine Bütüncül Yaklaşım: Etik, Teknolojik ve Eğitsel Boyutlarıyla Güncel Bir Derleme

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ABSTRACT

In medicine, privacy is a fundamental right that ensures the confidentiality of patients' health data. In today's rapidly digitizing world, the increasing complexity of collecting, storing, and sharing health data has made privacy a critical priority. Since healthcare services contain highly personal and sensitive information, any breach in this area can lead to severe consequences. The historical roots of privacy in healthcare can be traced back to the Hippocratic Oath, which explicitly states the physician's obligation to keep patient secrets. As modern medicine has advanced, so have patient-physician relationships and medical record-keeping practices. This evolution has made it necessary to strengthen privacy principles through robust legal and ethical regulations. The widespread adoption of electronic health records (EHRs) in the late 20th and early 21st centuries introduced new challenges to patient privacy. Today, comprehensive legal frameworks, such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), have been established in many countries to protect personal and health data. Protecting patient information is not merely a legal obligation; it is a fundamental ethical principle of professional healthcare. This review takes a holistic approach to patient privacy, examining it from ethical, technological, and educational perspectives. Current risks such as data breaches and privacy concerns related to artificial intelligence applications pose new threats to health data. To counter these, technological solutions such as encryption and anonymization are becoming increasingly important. Furthermore, it is crucial to enhance the knowledge and awareness of healthcare professionals regarding privacy. Educational programs are essential for this purpose. This review aims to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of patient privacy for healthcare administrators, professionals, and patients alike.

Keywords: Patient privacy, confidentiality, health data, ethics, technological solutions, education, electronic health records (EHR)

ÖZ

Tıp alanında mahremiyet, hastaların sağlık verilerinin gizliliğinin korunmasını ifade eden temel bir hak. Günümüzün dijitalleşen dünyasında, sağlık verilerinin toplanması, saklanması ve paylaşılmasındaki karmaşıklık, bu verilerin gizliliğini korumayı kritik bir öncelik haline getirmiştir. Sağlık hizmetleri kişisel ve hassas bilgiler içerdiğinden, bu alandaki gizliliğin ihlali ciddi sonuçlara yol açabilir. Sağlıkta gizliliğin tarihsel kökenleri Hipokrat Yemini'ne kadar uzanır; bu yeminde hekimlerin hasta sırlarını saklama yükümlülüğü belirtilmiştir. Modern tıbbın ilerlemesiyle hasta-hekim ilişkileri ve tıbbi kayıt pratikleri değişmiş, bu da gizlilik ilkesinin yasal ve etik düzenlemelerle güçlenmesini zorunlu kılmıştır. Özellikle 20. yüzyıl sonları ve 21. yüzyıl başlarında elektronik sağlık kayıtlarının (ESK) yaygınlaşmasıyla gizlilik konusu yeni boyutlar kazanmıştır. Günümüzde, Avrupa Birliği Genel Veri Koruma Tüzüğü (GDPR) gibi uluslararası düzenlemeler, kişisel ve sağlık verilerinin gizliliği için kapsamlı yasal çerçeveler oluşturmaktadır. Hasta bilgilerinin korunması, yalnızca yasal bir zorunluluk değil, aynı zamanda profesyonel düzeyde sağlık hizmeti sunmak için temel bir etik ilkedir. Bu derleme, hasta mahremiyetine bütüncül bir yaklaşımla konuyu etik, teknolojik ve eğitimsel açılardan ele almaktadır. Günümüzdeki veri ihlalleri ve yapay zeka gibi riskler, sağlık verilerinin korunması için yeni zorluklar ortaya çıkarmıştır. Bu risklere karşı şifreleme ve anonimleştirme gibi teknolojik çözümlerin kullanılması büyük önem taşır. Sağlık çalışanlarının mahremiyet konusundaki bilgi ve farkındalık düzeylerinin artırılması da hayati bir konudur. Bu amaçla, ilgili eğitim programlarının geliştirilmesi ve uygulanması gerekmektedir. Bu derleme, sağlık hizmetlerindeki yöneticiler, sağlık çalışanları ve hastalar için hasta mahremiyetinin kapsamlı bir şekilde anlaşılmasına katkıda bulunmayı hedeflemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Hasta mahremiyeti, gizlilik, sağlık verileri, etik, teknolojik çözümler, eğitim, elektronik sağlık kayıtları (ESK)

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INTRODUCTION

Privacy is defined as the autonomous right of individuals to determine when, how, and to what extent they share their personal information and physical and mental spaces with others (1). According to the Turkish Language Association (TDK), privacy, derived from the Arabic word “mahrem,” means “kept secret, not publicly disclosed or revealed”; terminologically, it is expressed as “secrecy, the secret state or aspect of something” (2,3).

Privacy in healthcare is an integral part of patient rights. This concept, considered as the “right to privacy in private life,” involves the protection of information about an individual’s private life. In the Patient Rights Regulation (HHY), privacy is defined as the confidential conduct of medical evaluations, the absence of unrelated persons during treatment, and the permission of the patient’s relatives to participate with the patient’s consent (4,5).

Privacy is examined not only in physical terms, but also in physical, communicative, and informational dimensions. Physical privacy refers to the space where the body is kept away from physical and visual contact. Communicative privacy encompasses the right of individuals to express their desires without verbal interference and to have them recorded. Information privacy emphasizes that personal information should not be shared with third parties without the individual’s consent (4). Article 21 of the Patient Rights Regulation clearly outlines this scope (5). Therefore, it is an ethical and professional obligation for healthcare professionals to be aware of privacy and to comply with these principles (6).

In the history of medical ethics, the principle of confidentiality has been one of the cornerstones of the medical profession since the Hippocratic Oath (7). The development of modern medicine, the proliferation of hospitals, and institutionalized healthcare services have transformed the concept of privacy beyond mere confidentiality into a multifaceted concept that also encompasses physical, communicative, and informational dimensions. Human rights movements in the 20th century reinforced the acceptance of privacy as a universal right.

The digital transformation process in recent years has created new risks in terms of privacy, despite efforts to protect patient safety. Violations of privacy can create psychological burdens in stressed individuals and negatively affect recovery processes. As the medical profession requires professional diligence and ensuring the welfare of society, the principles of privacy and confidentiality play a guiding role in clinical practice (7, 8).

Digitized healthcare systems, electronic health records, telemedicine applications, and AI-supported diagnostic systems have created fundamental changes in the collection, storage, processing, and sharing of patient data. This situation raises new ethical and legal dilemmas regarding data security and privacy protection. Big data

analysis and artificial intelligence applications give rise to complex discussions regarding the anonymization, re-identification, and consent processes of personal data.

In the education of medical, nursing, and midwifery students, privacy is generally addressed theoretically within the scope of ethics courses and patient rights legislation. Students gain comprehensive knowledge about the definition, dimensions, legal basis, and ethical principles of the concept. However, when it comes to clinical practice, it is often difficult to translate this knowledge into concrete applications. Heavy patient loads, inadequate infrastructure, or cultural differences can make it difficult to ensure ideal privacy conditions.

Medical students witness patients’ intimate moments during physical examinations and invasive procedures, nursing students during direct care processes, and midwifery students during prenatal, intrapartum, and postnatal care. These experiences allow students to understand how sensitive and multifaceted privacy is, as they have learned theoretically. Protecting patient privacy is not only a legal obligation but also an ethical responsibility that forms the basis of the patient-healthcare worker trust relationship and directly affects the quality of care.

This compilation examines the multidimensional importance of privacy in healthcare. Privacy is addressed in the training of all healthcare professionals, particularly medical, nursing, and midwifery students, both in terms of theoretical ethical principles and clinical practice dynamics. The study provides a comprehensive analysis in light of current literature, ranging from the definition of privacy to its historical evolution, the new challenges posed by digitizing healthcare systems, and the differences in translating theoretical knowledge into practical application.

FOUNDATIONS AND SCOPE OF PRIVACY

Patient privacy is an ethical and legal obligation that forms the basis of healthcare services. Ethically, it means respecting patient autonomy; protecting the individual’s right to make decisions about their own body and health (4). The relationship between healthcare professionals and patients being based on trust is directly linked to the protection of privacy (10). A patient-centered approach requires respect for physical, psychological, and social integrity (11).

Legally, privacy is guaranteed by the Patient Rights Regulation and the Personal Data Protection Law (KVKK) (12,13). These regulations protect the patient’s rights to be informed, to give consent, and to request the confidentiality of their personal information. Processes such as the confidentiality of electronic health records and the sharing of information with third parties are defined by the legal framework (14).

Types of privacy manifest themselves in different ways in practice. Physical privacy encompasses the non-

disclosure of the patient's body during examination and treatment and the appropriate arrangement of the care environment. Psychological privacy refers to respect for emotions, thoughts, and personal boundaries. Digital privacy involves ensuring the confidentiality of medical records stored electronically and protecting them against cyber access (16, 17).

The principle of authorized information sharing states that patient information can only be shared among healthcare professionals involved in the care process and that explicit consent must be obtained in other cases (17). Therefore, it is critically important for healthcare professionals to develop privacy awareness and demonstrate ethical attitudes in order to increase patient satisfaction and maintain a culture of trust (18).

PRIVACY AWARENESS IN HEALTH EDUCATION

Instilling privacy awareness in healthcare professionals as part of a systematic and comprehensive training program during their professional identity formation process is one of the cornerstones of effective patient care (20). Particularly in medical schools, raising students' awareness of patient rights and privacy issues early on is critically important in preparing them for clinical practice (21).

The development of privacy awareness should not be limited to theoretical ethics courses; it should be reinforced in a multidimensional way through clinical practice (22). Privacy is generally addressed in medical school curricula within the scope of professional ethics, patient rights, and communication skills; however, the complexity of situations students encounter in clinical practice makes it difficult to fully internalize this information (23). Therefore, students' ethical knowledge and practical skills must be supported in a holistic manner.

During clinical rotations, students may observe privacy-respecting practices as well as witness boundary violations (24). Therefore, it is important to organize clinical training environments in a way that prioritizes privacy (27). Simulations and OSCE (Objective Structured Clinical Examination) applications are effective tools for developing privacy awareness and communication skills

in medical school (26). These methods offer students the opportunity to practice protecting privacy in a realistic but controlled environment (27).

The development of privacy awareness can be assessed through structured observation forms, simulation-based scenarios, and OSCE stations. In these exams, students are scored on their ability to maintain confidentiality when communicating with patients, ensure privacy during examinations, and make ethical decisions. Below is an example OSCE assessment table for measuring privacy awareness in medical students.

This table serves to reinforce privacy awareness in health education through measurable and observable behaviors. Student performance in OSCE and simulation-based sessions can be evaluated according to these criteria. Thus, an effective bridge is established between theoretical knowledge and clinical practice, and students are supported in gaining competence in ethical, physical, and communicative privacy practices.

PRIVACY AWARENESS IN MEDICAL, NURSING, AND MIDWIFERY STUDENTS

Patient privacy is one of the fundamental ethical principles of healthcare services and is a responsibility that must be embraced by all healthcare professionals. Therefore, developing privacy awareness in the education process of medical, nursing, and midwifery students is of great importance (24). Education programs aim to provide these student groups with ethical, legal, and practical knowledge; however, educational approaches in different disciplines create diversity in the perception of privacy (27).

Medical students learn the ethical and legal aspects of privacy theoretically and try to put this knowledge into practice in clinical settings. However, under the pressure of heavy patient loads and professional responsibilities, they may experience difficulties in protecting privacy (34). In contrast, nursing and midwifery students experience both the physical and psychosocial dimensions of privacy more frequently because they are more directly involved in the care process (17). This situation demonstrates that discipline-specific educational models and clinical roles have a decisive impact on privacy awareness (22).

Table 1. Example of Patient Privacy Assessment in OSCE.

Assessment Area	Observed Behavior	Scoring Scale (1-5)	Explanation / Observation Note
Protection of physical privacy	Curtaining before examination, closing the door, avoiding unnecessary exposure	1-5	1 = not observed at all, 5 = fully implemented
Informing and obtaining consent	Providing an explanation before the examination and obtaining the patient's consent	1-5	Verbal explanation, consent verification
Protection of personal data	Not sharing patient information with third parties, file confidentiality	1-5	Was any verbal or written breach of confidentiality observed?
Respectful communication	Form of address, body language, sensitivity to the patient's boundaries	1-5	Eye contact, tone of voice, listening skills
Intervention in case of privacy violation	Demonstrating corrective behavior when privacy is compromised	1-5	Drawing a curtain, issuing a warning, etc., when necessary

Educators setting an example and the rigorous application of privacy standards in clinical settings are important factors in increasing students' awareness (26). Therefore, it is necessary to integrate theoretical and practical components that strengthen privacy awareness into the curricula of medical, nursing, and midwifery programs (27).

In conclusion, developing privacy awareness is possible through an interdisciplinary educational structure, privacy-appropriate clinical practice environments, and the contribution of educators who are sensitive to ethical values. Such an approach ensures that students grow up to be respectful of patient rights, possess high ethical standards, and become sensitive healthcare professionals (27). In this context, the development of privacy awareness has become an important area of research not only for medical school students but also for students in different health disciplines.

DIGITALIZATION AND PRIVACY: THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In modern healthcare, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies process a wide range of data, from electronic health records to radiological images (28). While machine learning algorithms analyze patient data to develop personalized medical applications, they also pose new challenges for protecting patient privacy (32).

Data Collection and Processing Processes

AI-supported healthcare systems collect demographic information, medical history, genetic data, and real-time physiological parameters using a multidimensional approach (33). Remote patient monitoring systems provide a continuous flow of data from patients' daily lives, requiring a redefinition of privacy boundaries (34).

Legal Regulations

Legal regulations such as HIPAA and GDPR set strict standards for the processing of health data. However, the need for AI algorithms to access large data sets renders traditional data protection approaches insufficient (34).

AI Interactions in the Clinical Setting

Patients are constantly interacting with AI systems in daily healthcare through hospital information systems, diagnostic support tools, and robotic surgical systems (7). Although these technologies have high potential to improve the patient experience, patients' awareness of these systems remains low (25).

Telemedicine and Remote Healthcare Services

Telemedicine applications, which became widespread after the COVID-19 pandemic, have enabled AI-supported diagnosis and treatment systems to reach

patients' homes (7). Virtual assistants and remote patient monitoring systems expand the traditional boundaries of patient-physician interaction while creating new challenges in privacy protection (33).

Mobile Health Applications

Smartphone applications and wearable health devices constitute the areas where patients come into the most direct contact with AI technologies (33). While these devices have the potential to improve quality of life with their continuous data collection capabilities, there is a lack of transparency regarding the sharing of personal data with third parties (30).

Ethical Principles and Digital Health

The fundamental principles of health ethics—autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice—are being reinterpreted in the era of digital health (32). Patient autonomy includes the right to understand how personal health data is used in AI systems and to have a say in these processes (25).

Informed Consent and AI Systems

Traditional informed consent processes are inadequate in the face of the complexity of AI algorithms (33). Dynamic consent models and layered information systems are being developed to help patients understand how their data is used in machine learning processes (34).

Data Ownership and Patient Rights

In the age of AI, the ownership and control rights of patient data have become complex. Patients' right to access their own health data, their authority to request the deletion of this data, and data portability form the fundamental areas of debate in digital health ethics (34).

CONCLUSION

Patient privacy constitutes an integral dimension of healthcare within the framework of ethical principles and is shaped on the basis of respect for individual dignity. Digitalization, increased data sharing, and heavy clinical workloads make it difficult to protect this principle. Therefore, privacy must be addressed not only as a theoretical ethical concept but also as an observable behavior in clinical practice.

To strengthen privacy awareness in educational processes, it is recommended that practical assessment methods such as OSCE and simulation-based training be used in addition to ethics and patient rights courses in the curriculum. These methods allow students' ability to apply privacy principles in realistic scenarios to be measured. Furthermore, regular awareness training, feedback mechanisms, and institutional control tools should be developed in healthcare institutions to address privacy violations.

Ultimately, protecting patient privacy will only be possible through the comprehensive implementation of ethical, technological, and educational strategies. In this context, developing concrete tools that facilitate the measurement and evaluation of privacy (e.g., the OSCE evaluation form shown in **Table 1**) will strengthen the bridge between education and practice. Furthermore, it is recommended that standard measurement tools be integrated into medical, nursing, and midwifery programs to monitor and develop privacy awareness. Students' communication, physical, and ethical privacy practices can be observed and scored through OSCE stations and simulation sessions. Educators can reinforce these measurement results through feedback and self-assessment sessions to support students' behavioral development. Similarly, standardizing privacy practices through continuous supervision, mentor support, and institutional protocols in clinical settings ensures that graduating healthcare professionals are respectful of patient rights and have a high sense of ethical responsibility.

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